

SMART GRID DEMAND SIDE MANAGEMENT USING IoT LOAD CONTROL METHOD

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Abstract

Innovative market for energy have undergone a transformation with the introduction of smart grids, which enable users to participate in demand response (DR) programs and achieve a balance between energy supply and demand. It can be difficult for users to respond to DR signals since they are typically less aware of what to do when they get one. With the use of DR signals, energy management controllers, or EMCs, were developed to automatically solve energy management issues. Rather than turning off a feeder, we have solved this issue automatically or from the smart grid by controlling individual loads using Arduino, ESP-8266, relays, and an online application or website. With this EMC integration into our current network, we will be able to remotely adjust load, lower the cost of electricity per unit, enhance power quality, and prevent peaks during off-peak hours. As a consequence, we were able to accomplish our necessary goals with our current infrastructure by using hardware and software solutions.

Index Terms: Operator Demand Side Management; Demand Side Management Utilizing IoT; Demand Management for Smart Grids; Internet of Things in the Intelligent Grid.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increase in quality of life, urbanization, and innovations in technology have all led to an increase in energy usage. If the issue is not effectively handled, it will be impossible to manage this significantly increased energy demand. Cities make up 80% of the release of greenhouse gases and 75–80% of total energy use. Global environmental preservation and sustainable energy are both impacted by this horrifying reality [1, 2].

A power grid is a system in which the distribution of electrical energy is managed centrally. Despite advances in technology throughout this time, the structure and operating concept of the electricity grid remain similar from its inception to the present. The main functions of these conventional power grids are electricity production, control, and distribution [3].

The following problems affect these power networks. Blackouts, low power quality, significant transmission losses, dependability, and integrating distributed power sources into the system. Furthermore, it is not feasible to monitor and regulate in real time in a typical power system. A smart grid provides an answer to these issues. The smart grid's

efficient use of energy and integration of renewable resources will benefit the ecosystem as well as the power system. The Smart Grid seeks to improve the economics of operations, maintenance, and planning in addition to grid observability, asset control, power system performance, and security [4]. Smart grid systems are described as information management, control technologies, digitally based sensing, communication technologies, & field devices that work together to coordinate diverse electric operations according to the US Department of Energy's Smart Grid System Report [5]. The ability to (1) track or analyze operations, convey information back to operation facilities, and frequently respond automatically to modify an activity; (2) exchange information among appliances and networks; & (3) process, examine, & support service providers in utilizing & analyzing data generated by digital technologies across the grid are the three main ways that these smart grid technologies have impacted the traditional grid operation & planning problems. A possible method of depicting the Smart Grid is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1.1: Smart Grid Overview

The goal of electrical power management is to lower energy costs while simultaneously modifying the supply and consumption side load profiles. Increasing operational efficiency of power production, distribution, and transmission is the goal of supply-side management (SSM). SSM offers a number of benefits, including as minimizing the negative environmental effects, meeting demand for power without the need to build additional infrastructure, and boosting customer value by guaranteeing optimal energy generation at the lowest feasible cost. The unpredictability of fuel prices brought on by thermal generator control strategies is a challenge for supply-side management, albeit [6].

Demand-side management (DSM) represents an additional strategy for electrical power management. By regularly tracking energy consumption and altering appliance timetables, DSM minimizes the expense of energy purchase & related penalties [7]. The electrical sector established the DSM in 1970 with the goals of reducing peak usage, controlling power demand at the time of use (TOU) levels, reducing emission of carbon dioxide, evaluating user profiles for electricity loads, & giving customers a selection of favored power sources [8].

Demand side management is one of the key components of the energy management of the future smart grid [9, 10]. It provides assistance for the operations of the smart grid in several domains, such as the construction of structures, the administration of decentralized energy resources, and the regulation and control of the electrical market. Suppressing and regulating energy demand can decrease the requirement for peak loads, change the demand profile, and improve grid sustainability by lowering overall expenses and reducing carbon emissions. Appropriate demand scheduling might help avoid an underutilized electrical system in terms of distribution networks, transmission lines, and generation capacity.

Smart price adjustment is one distinctive feature of the smart grid, enabled by the automated metering infrastructure's use of intelligent metering instruments [11], [12]. In the framework of the smart grid, demand-side control is being implemented with the intention of boosting efficiency of the system, sustainability, & security. By making the most of the capacity of the current network & assisting in the integration of green technologies into the network, this is achieved.

Thanks to a technology known as the Internet of Things (IoT), devices may be connected to one another and distantly analyzed over the web. Over the last few years, the concept of the "Internet of Things" has seen substantial development & is being used in a number of contexts, including telemedicine, smart homes, industrial settings, and more [13]. The Internet of Things (IoT) includes wireless sensor network technologies that enable smart objects with enhanced capabilities to be networked globally [14].

Due to growing energy costs, environmental damage, and enticing renewable legislative perks, consumers are shifting more and more towards energy sources that are renewable. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions requires giving the utility system less priority when using easily available renewable energy sources. Minimizing carbon dioxide emissions is a great advantage, but Distributed Generations' (DGs') outages jeopardize the reliability of the grid. DSM is a very promising technology when it comes to Smart Grids, since it can reduce power generation, restrict the buyer energy usage, and make the grid more predictable and more stable. The Demand Response (DR) programme, energy efficiency programme, and all energy conservation programme forms the foundation of DSM's schematic strategy.

The traditional approach to meeting the required energy demand is to build more producing capacity [15, 16]. Air pollution, climate change, and the rapid loss of natural

resources are some of the obstacles that come with greater generation capacity [17]. In addition, there are a number of obstacles facing newly developed renewable energy sources, such as wind turbines and photovoltaic (PV): high initial prices and fluctuating performance [18, 19]. Demand response (DR) is therefore essential for balancing the amount of producing power that is available against the demand for power [20, 21]. DR is the term used to describe how modifications in energy prices or incentives cause the habits of consumer use to alter [22].

Information and communication technology (ICT) improvements have made it feasible for smart dwellings that enable optimum control for easier monitoring by connecting all home sensors & appliances across a home area network (HAN) [23, 24]. Nonetheless, flexible DR systems are made possible by the availability of many pricing alternatives. Because of this, consumers have a great deal of opportunity to manage load scheduling through the use of current smart home technologies [25].

Technologies including Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Zigbee, Arduino, and GSM are frequently utilised in home automation. Every technology has benefits and drawbacks. Zigbee protocol was used for recording temperature by Ransing and Rajput [26] as it consumes less power. A smart house system developed by Kumar and Lee [27] made use of sensors and Bluetooth technology. RESTful web services were used by them as the interoperable layer. For the purpose of giving and receiving orders, they developed an application for Android. A Zigbee-based smart automation system designed by Young-Guk Ha [28] has been evaluated for surveillance and alert applications. Magnet sensors were affixed to a door or window for home security. Noguchi, Mori, and Sato [29] have looked into sensor data collecting and smart sensor evaluation of human activity in short. They used sensor data to predict people's actions and tried to compare them to the initial routines.

Brundha and Lakshmi [30] constructed the home automation system with the goal of enhancing the security system. With the help of this technology, the owner can receive details regarding an unknown person who entered the place by receiving images taken by a camera that is integrated into the automation system. An Android application with voice activation was developed by Soundhari and Sangeetha [31] to operate the devices. In this case, there is no other method to regulate it; the user has to download the application for Android. An Android app controls a Bluetooth-based sensor application designed and built by Chiao, Yuan, and Shiau-Chin [32].

Current Bluetooth-based systems for automation are easy to set up and reasonably priced, though they are not adaptable to changing environmental conditions or have a limited amount of usage capacity. In general, Bluetooth systems have a range of 0 to 15 metres. In addition, Bluetooth is an outdated technology with probably compatibility issues. As a result of their limited suitability for inside situations, ZigBee-based systems also have range problems. The following are the main issues with current home automation systems: Poor management, high expenses for implementation, and little flexibility to satisfy customer needs.

The structure of this research study is as follows: The pertinent work is presented in Chapter 2, the research methodology is shown in Chapter 3, and the basic idea is illustrated in Chapter 4. Results and debates are covered in Chapter 5, and future attempts are covered in Chapter 6.

2. RELATED WORK

By scheduling AOAs, smart grid research seeks to enhance the management of electricity. Samadi et al. (2010) develop plug-in hybrid electric automobiles [33]. The introduction of new electrical devices with enormous power needs has led to an increase in consumer usage of electricity & power system problems. Power producing companies may decide to schedule energy-efficient devices or construct new facilities in order to meet client demands. The most costly method, which necessitates a large financial outlay, is constructing fresh power stations in addition to currently operational ones to increase output. As a result, electricity transmission & distribution will get increasingly complex.

The second tactic is to fulfil current requirements by offering several price alternatives. Methods for a full day. A direct load control approach is described by Abdollahi et al. (2011) [34]. The DLC technique allows utilities to control both peak and off-peak power demand by providing subsidies to consumers to move load to low-demand times and limit use during peak hours.

An inclining block rate (IBR) with TOU & RPT is utilised, according to Zhao et al. (2013) and Rastegar et al. (2016), to avert peaks during non-peak hours [35, 36]. By scheduling appliances based on TOU pricing rules, the system that manages energy in the home was developed by Abushnaf et al. (2016) [37], which proposed the HEMS algorithm to lower power expenses and utilisation. HEMS is used by Zhou et al. (2016) [38] to plan, control, and monitor AOAs. To lower the peak to average proportion, HEMSs allot a specific time window to each apparatus. Using price signals from electrical enterprises, automated machinery is scheduled during this period. Certain appliances—like juicers, blenders, and kettles—do not receive enough attention even if they have been featured in a number of articles.

Long durations have disadvantages, although they also make users less comfortable, claim Ma et al. (2016) [39]. User convenience is defined by Zhou et al. (2016) [40] as reducing device latency and energy consumption. Convenience for the customer must be considered in efforts to reduce power use. The absence of renewable energy sources in the previously mentioned investigation is one of its major shortcomings. According to Zafar et al. (2013) [41], renewable energy sources are crucial to any power system and are included in the Smart Grid. Adika and Wang (2014) describe MINLP using RTP, which timetables thermal and electrical equipment to maximise energy savings and improve user comfort. A lot of models function well. However, this strategy's computing complexity is a disadvantage. The writers spoke about user-initiated scheduling device modifications. Jovanovic and colleagues (2016) [42]. Nevertheless, the necessary adjustments had to

wait until the following day, which further infuriated the clients. The answer to this problem was discovered by Hafeez et al. (2019) by allowing the user to toggle between gadgets at their desire. A linear programming-based energy storage system was presented by Wang and Adika (2014) [43] to reduce peak demand and electricity costs by almost a factor of five. Evolutionary algorithm (EA) was used by Azar and Jacobsen (2016) [44] to accomplish three objectives: reducing the cost of energy, raising the demand for power, and reducing carbon emissions that are not needed.

Elkazaz et al. (2016) [45] employed distributed generation (DG) to provide two-way current flow in order to lower electrical expenses and equipment latencies. On the other hand, installation, maintenance, and operating expenditures were just ignored. In order to reduce peak demand and electricity expenditures, Sivasubramani & Lokeshgupta (2019) [46] & Muhsen and colleagues (2019) [47] used linear programming (LP) and EA.

The technologies of home automation & safety systems enable homeowners to make better and more economical use of their house's appliances, lighting, heating, & cooling units. It might be as basic as a remote control or some automated lighting, or it may involve a sophisticated system that manages every necessary part of a house & is customised to meet your unique requirements [48].

A mobile may be used to remotely operate household items from any part of the globe using an Internet of Things (IoT)-based home automation and safety control system. Although the term could also refer to isolated programmable devices like thermostats and sprinkler systems, the term "automation of the house" more accurately describes homes where almost every electrical feature—including lights, appliances, heating and cooling systems, and outlets—can be adjusted online. A complete home security system includes a fire alarm system, secure locks on all windows and doors, smoke detectors, surveillance cameras, and other sensors that are linked to guarantee the security and safety of the house [49]. A key component of contemporary home automation involves accessibility and monitoring via the internet. Even while one-sided monitoring via the internet has been available for a while, it wasn't until the invention of tablets and smartphones that we could connect to our home networks while on the go. Any equipment with an Internet connection may see and operate a home automation system, along with any associated devices. Basic notifications may be used for many important purposes. You may set up your surveillance system to send you an email or text message whenever it detects anything that might be amiss, such as a fire alarm, a moving object warning, or an extreme weather alert. Alerts for less unusual situations may also be sent to you; for example, you might set up your "smart" front door lock to alert you when your kid gets home from their institution.

This method offers helpful material on energy management. Certain models work well under specific conditions. For example, one method considered PAR, while another focused on energy costs, and some methods combined the two. However, other models weighed the expense against user comfort and emissions of carbon dioxide. The prior method does not take into consideration most of the benefits of smart grids, including

peak power, energy prices, quality of power, and outages. IoT-based smart grid infrastructure for demand side control is not the main topic of these research. Our investigation suggests an IOT base system to solve peak power, blackouts, energy prices, and power quality with this goal in mind.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Why Demand side management?

Demand cannot be balanced with the available resources due to the residential, commercial and vehicle to grid load growing so rapidly. Also, conventional sources contribute to warming and are depletable. That's why only supply side management is not enough now a days so we need demand side management too.

Due to earlier published incentive-based demand management, by users, it can cause problem if user do not care for cost.

Problems:

Blackout

Power quality will be degraded

Cost per unit will be high

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Figure 4.1: Proposed system architecture

5. METHODOLOGY

Utilising computers or smartphones, consumer side management in smart grid technology relies on the Internet of Things (IoT) and controls connected customers' loads via the web. Node MCU is used in the development of the proposed system, which solves all of the drawbacks of previous methods. All of the sensors in this project are connected to the main Arduino Nano microcontroller, which is connected to the Node MCU controller board. The outcomes are displayed on a computer or smartphone through bidirectional Internet of Things communication. In the section on the proposed system design, a block diagram is used to illustrate it. We use a variety of sensors in this network, each with a specialised purpose. For instance, the temperature sensor measures the temperature and humidity of the outside air and alerts us about possible risks of fire in the event that something akin to a short circuit occurs in the vicinity of this apparatus. The LCD shows the voltage, current, and connected load to the system. The loads are connected to the relays, which turn them on and off as needed.

5.1 Components List

The major components of the system are as follows.

- 1) AT mag328 Microcontroller
- 2) ESP 8266 Microcontroller (Node MCU)
- 3) Voltage sensor
- 4) Current sensor
- 5) Temperature sensor
- 6) Relays
- 7) Computer or Android phone
- 8) LCD type Display

5.2 AT mag328 microcontroller

Users' devices connected to it are managed by the microcontroller. Under the given conditions, it utilises the programming to control the equipment. The size and quantity of pins on the Arduino board allow it to be divided into several groups. These microcontrollers are called MEGA, UNO, and NANO. A code written in Arduino utilising a C-programming variation will be put into the Arduino microcontroller. The software will command the microcontroller to retrieve control information from a cloud web server located on the internet. Through the WiFi module, data will be gathered on a regular basis. There are several methods available for connecting an Arduino microcontroller to the web. Using the Arduino UNO WiFi device is one method. Included on the microcontroller board is a WiFi module. Using an ESP8266 WiFi module UNO alone is an additional choice. It is an Arduino-designed controller board that is based on the Atmega328 CPU. Electronic devices are becoming progressively more compact, affordable, and functional,

which enables them to accomplish more jobs than their predecessors, which were bulkier, costly, and limited in what they could accomplish. Automation experts are always searching for new and creative methods for improvement that require the least amount of work and yield the greatest outcomes. The introduction of the microcontroller to the electronics industry aimed to simplify our tasks, including remote links with automation of any kind.

Figure 5.1: Arduino-Nano Board

Microcontrollers are widely used in systems that are embedded, which enable devices to operate in accordance with human needs and requirements. Among the controllers are ATMEGA 328, ATMEGA 16, PIC16F877, and 8051. The Arduino UNO model is a very practical piece of hardware, with an Atmega 328 microcontroller, 6 analogue function pins, 14 digital I/O pins, and a USB port. Serial mode communication is also supported via the Rx & Tx ports. Although there are more board models on the market, such as the Arduino Leonardo, Arduino UNO, Arduino Mega, and Arduino Due, the Arduino Mega and Arduino Uno are the most often utilised. For simplicity and affordability, the Arduino Uno model is the best option.

Arduino-Board

Arduino is an open-source electronics platform with limited hardware and software. With the numerous inputs that Arduino boards can take and convert into outputs, anything may be done, such as turning on an LED, starting a motor, or publishing anything online. A tweet, a finger pushing a button, or light from a sensor are a few examples of these inputs.

Figure 5.2: Arduino-Board

5.3 ESP 8266 Microcontroller (Node MCU)

Primarily designed for Internet of Things applications, the freely available Node MCU developmental board and firmware are built on the Lua programming language. Included are hardware components based on the ESP-12 module and firmware for Espressif Systems' ESP8266 Wi-Fi SoC.

Figure 5.3: ESP 8266 Microcontroller (Node MCU)

Here are the instructions to help you enjoy your first time using the Arduino IDE and Node MCU!

- Step 1: Connect the Node MCU to your PC.
- Step 2: The next step is to install the serial port driver (COM).
- Step 3: Installing version 1.6.4 or above of the Arduino IDE is the third step.
- Step 4: Install the ESP8266 board package that you downloaded in step 4.
- Step 5: Setting Up Support for ESP8266 is the Last Step.

5.4 Relays

An electrical switch is called a relay. Many relays used electromagnetic fields to carry out a function; when too much current flowed, their coils gained energy and carried out the interruption function. There are currently other performance benchmarks in use as well.

Figure 5.4: Relay

Relays are employed when a single sign must control several circuits or when a low-control signal must be utilised to manage a circuit with complete electrical isolation between the controlled and control circuits. The essential relays were used to build long parcel display circuits that repeated and sent the sign from one area to the other. Relays were widely employed to do mundane activities in early computers and phone trading systems. Applying an overcurrent to the coil creates an attracting field that starts the armature. Depending on advancement, the next improvement of the appropriate contacts will either make a contact with a fixed contact or speak to the element of truth.

If the contacts' course of action had been discontinued when trade was halted, the improvement reopens the contact, ends the affiliation, and maintains the openness of the other connections. The armature returns to its rested state with a force that is approximately half that of the attracting power once the circle's current is taken off. This power is typically provided by a spring, although more complex engine starters are using gravity instead. Fast completion is the goal of most agreements. This reduces arcing in high-voltage or current applications and removes misinterpretation in low-voltage applications.

6. BASIC OPERATION OF IOT BASED SYSTEM

6.1 Blynk

How should the application's layout be created? You can quickly develop interfaces for tracking and managing equipment with the latest Blynk platform, iOS, and Android smartphones. You may customise your project dashboard by arranging buttons, sliders, graphs, and other elements on the screen after downloading the Blynk programme. Not only is the Blynk app available for free on iOS and Android devices, but the Blynk server and library are also freely available. Let's say that whenever you click on an icon on the Blynk app, a message is transmitted to the Blynk Cloud and beyond, and subsequently it displays on your smart grid without any explanation. Every detail occurs in the ripping of an eye, and it operates in the same way in the opposite direction. You may download Blynk for free, and there are no continuing costs. To get started, simply create an account on this application. Install Blynk on an iOS or Android device.

6.2 Operating Principle of our Proposed System

This system consists of two main components: hardware and software. An Arduino board, a Node MCU, sensors, relays, and a connected load make up the hardware. Home appliance controls are operated by these physical parts. A connection between the hardware application and the software will be provided by the Arduino board. The programme comprises of code for embedded platforms (micro-controllers) and a programme for Android. The board that makes up the Arduino will facilitate the establishment of a link between the software and hardware. The Android app is made on a web-based graphical programming language, but the code is written in embedded C.

To monitor the load current and energy consumption, an ACS 712 type Hall effect sensor is connected in series with the associated load. Consequently, it receives all of the spent current. The output of the sensor is sent to an Arduino board for further processing, which computes the quantity of current. In a similar vein, we use a potential divider to monitor voltage. This device transforms the input voltage into a corresponding low voltage that can then be measured using an Arduino. The Arduino measures both voltage and current, and then sends the data to a cloud-based server via a serial connection (UART). From there, the information is loaded to the Android app's graphical user interface. The GUI has buttons for controlling connected loads in addition to voltage and current knobs. A control signal is created and sent to the cloud-based server when buttons on the GUI Android app are pressed. The Wi-Fi board (Node MCU) receives this signal and turns the connected load.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following table shows assumed Load for our research.

Table7.1: Assumed load

Transformer#1	
Load of consumers	Rated Power (KW)
Essential	500
Non- Essential	300
Transformer#2	
Load of consumers	Rated Power (KW)
Essential	500
Non- Essential	300
Transformer#3	
Load of consumers	Rated Power (KW)
Essential	500
Non- Essential	300

Non-Essential appliances

Non-Essential loads are those that can be interrupted and rescheduled for usage at another time.

Essential Appliances

Essential appliances are those that need to be switched on or off without delay as per the consumer's requirement.

Red-lines: Out of acceptable range.

The results obtained from above network by simulation shows that bus voltage is beyond the acceptable limit, and the red color cables are of the wrong size, being undersized.

1) Cable sizing:

So, suitable cable selected.

2) Transformer selection: The transformer was loaded to 80% of its rated power.

The transformer's capacity was reached by raising the demand to 80% of its capacity, which led to inadequate cables and voltage drops that were higher than permitted.

a) Now again select suitable cable.

Above simulation shows all cables suitably selected.

b) Additionally, the transformer must be sized to handle a load of 120% (i.e., only 80% load).

Transformer sized appropriately. Every transformer has a size based on the entire load. Buses that are outside of the allowable voltage range are shown by red lines.

Voltage adjustment according to allowed range of voltage:

When the voltage and frequency exceed allowable limits, the system becomes unstable. This variation occurs due to an imbalance between supply and demand power, giving us two options to address this issue.

- a) The first step in load management is to boost generation capacity;
- b) The second step is to reduce load.

We are at the maximum Generation limit during peak hours, thus we are unable to pursue the first alternative, which is to boost the Generation. Therefore, the only option left for demand response in demand side management is to reduce the load. Let's disconnect ALL non-essential loads to see the outcome.

The pink lines represent the buses, indicating that they are now within the permitted voltage variation's allowable marginal range. This indicates that reducing non-essential load on the demand side aids in system stabilisation. which demand side management refers to as the DR approach.

Remote management and cost savings:

Power providers will need to operate peak power plants during peak hours in order to meet demand if load is high. When compared to off-peak hours, prices are higher during peak hours (when peak plants are activated). So, if the utility companies will limit the load to base load plant capacity, by the proposed method, it will lessen the peak, which will ultimately lower the price of the power used.

As an example, we've looked at an 11 KV feeder that includes three transformers, each of which has a 500 KW essential load and a 300 kW non-essential load. Thus, the outcomes for the subsequent cases are displayed below. when

- 1) Only essential load is connected as on.
- 2) Essential and non-essential load both are connected as on.

In our simulation we have considered 1.5MW as Base load and any load above that is considered as peak load. The price per MW is \$500 for base load and it is \$1300 for load beyond the base load as highlighted in blue colour. It can be seen from the plotted graph that as the system is burdened by the load beyond the base load the cost per unit increases for all the consumers connected to the system. In the graph the line after 1.5MW donot follow the same linear increase but has changed to a different linear increase of price due to use of in-efficient peak plants to meet the demand at peak time.

The cost of the system when only the base load is connected is depicted in the above graph. It is evident that the cost of power delivered to customers remains constant per unit. And the reason for this is because our suggested controller has limited our power usage to base load, preventing the need for expensive and inefficient peak power plants.

And anybody with log-in credentials may manage this controller online from any location around the globe.

Reliability Improvement:

It is evident that a malfunction in a big load can cause the system to become unstable since the voltage would decrease and the current will rise. As a result, excessive current will damage network components, lowering system dependability. By using our built controller to remotely cut off the problematic load from the network, we can boost system dependability by allowing the other, healthy load to continue operating dependably.

Fig-1: Rate of component failure

f/ yr: depicts yearly failure

Case 1: Cutting off Non-Essential load 1

We assumed that the fault is happening on the non-essential load side for our simulation. In this instance, we have determined that Load-1 is at fault. As shown in figs. 1 and 2, it is evident that by removing the problematic load-1 from the operational network using the suggested approach, the bus failure rate has decreased from 0.854 f/yr to 0.83 f/yr.

Fig-2

Case 2: Unplugging Non-essential loads 1 and 2

We assumed that the problem is occurring on the non-essential load side for our simulation. We have determined that Loads 1 and 2 are at fault in this instance. As shown in Figs. 2 and 3, it is evident that by removing the problematic loads, 1 and 2, from the operational network using the suggested method, the bus failure rate has decreased from 0.83 f/yr to 0.806 f/yr.

Fig-3

Case 3: Unplugging Non-essential loads 1, 2, and 3.

We assumed that the problem is occurring on the non-essential load side for our simulation. In this instance, we have determined that Load-1 is at fault. As shown in Figs. 3 and 4, it is evident that by removing the problematic loads 1, 2, and 3 from the operational network using the suggested method, the bus failure rate has decreased from 0.806 f/yr to 0.781 f/yr.

Fig-4

Enhance power quality and prevent peaks during off-peak hours: In the literature study described above, customers handled demand-side load control. Thus, the problem we face is that if every customer shift all of their load to off-peak hours and turns it on simultaneously, then another peak—which may be greater than supply—will occur.

Therefore, in our suggested technique, load is regulated by smart grid operator using IOT to prevent it from occurring. The operator continually monitors frequency and voltage, and he is alerted to an imbalance in power supply and demand anytime he notices a variation from the usual values. So, balancing power generation and load consumption balance all the time, by switching off the exceeded load by this technique, makes the power supply to be of excellent quality. It means that he cuts off the non-essential load from his grid station since it shows that the load has grown from the base load during peak hour. This prevents the peak from occurring during peak or any other off-peak period. The figs. above use simulation to demonstrate this.

Control at Your Fingertips: We can install an app on our phones called Blynk. After registering, we must specify the load in this programme according to essential & non-essential loads. We must connect the Arduino to the necessary load in accordance with its categories & maintain an online connection. Thus, by utilising the log-in credentials, we may access our load for control from anywhere in the world. Alternatively, special purpose applications may be created and utilised from anywhere in the globe for more security.

8. CONCLUSION

The current DR can lower energy costs because to user apathy and lack of understanding, but it is unable to handle problems with blackouts, power quality, and remote control. Based on the results obtained, we may infer that this suggested solution will lessen power quality problems, the likelihood of blackouts, and the cost per unit.

9. FUTURE WORK

The following are some ways that this study can be expanded in the years to come.

- 1) An automated system has to be designed for this purpose, rather than the smart grid operator monitoring the voltage and frequency to evaluate power quality and blackout concerns.
- 2) Renewable sources may be connected to the feeder leaving the distribution smart grid at various locations, and the CO₂ emissions and cost effect per unit can then be examined.
- 3) Instead of using a smart grid operator, an AI system may be utilised to anticipate load and automatically operate Arduino.
- 4) A distribution smart grid may integrate renewable energy sources, energy storage, and artificial intelligence (AI) for load prediction. It can then analyse the impact on CO₂ emissions and unit costs.

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